

THEORETICAL ISSUES OF THE CONCEPT OF COGNITIVISM

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Annotation: this article is analyzed from the theoretical side of the concept of cognitivism, the most relevant area of linguistics, and focuses on the ideas put forward by many scientists.

Key words: cognitivism, psychology-physics, logic, neurophysiology, biology, mental thinking, conceptual, linguistic, linguistic, artificial intelligence, perception.

In the following years, as a result of the emergence of cognitive analysis in linguistics, cognitive linguistics was formed as a separate direction and became one of the most relevant, which occupies a solid place in linguistics. At this point, it would be appropriate to interpret the concept of cognitivism and aspects of its connection with the science of linguistics.

Cognitivism is an original philosophical concept that terminologically represents different meanings in different disciplines. In particular, in the "dictionary of philosophy" this word

1. Cognitivism – (lot. Cognitio-knowledge, cognition) is a term used in modern Western sociology of Science, in the theory of philosophy of cognition, to refer to the aspect of precisely knowledge (which is different from the social side that defines science or interacts with it.

2. Cognitivism or, in accordance with knowledge, a concept that expresses the possibility of knowing an event.

3. Scientific ideas and information about objects related to the achievement of the goal", while in the philosophical encyclopedic dictionary published in Moscow "Cognitivnie (lot. Cognitio-znanie, poznanie), poznavayemyy, sotvetstvuyutshie poznaniyu", is defined as.

And in pedagogy," education to expand the range of knowledge about the cognitive – environmental sphere, to form a differentiating thinking, to develop cognitive needs", focuses on its pedagogical aspect, and it differs in the direction of Education. "Cognition is the process of independent thinking of an individual. Cognitive education-education and training of children with special talents. Cognitive style-1) specific cognitive characteristics that the individual uses in the strategy of the process of cognition; 2) a control method according to a set of specially selected tests or a set of indicators of private cognition", also approached as.

The cognitive term " in general "is derived from the English" cognize – (knowledge, comprehension, understanding)", and cognitivism is not limited to the knowledge of the existing theory in philosophy. He studies the relationship of language and thinking, mental, physiological and biological processes in the process of thinking, in close connection with social, linguistic, linguistic phenomena and processes in the human mind. As the great linguist Ayub Gulomov noted, "the interdependence of language and thinking does not consist in the expression of thought through language: thinking itself is born in the language base, thought does not live without language material"

In general, the term "cognitive" refers to the cognitive and associated psycho-physiological, logical, neurophysiological, biological processes that occur in the human mind. These processes are studied directly in connection with the National-mental nature of man, his way of thinking.

In this context, cognitive linguistics is associated with Psycholinguistics in the first gal, which focuses on the psychological aspects of linguistic phenomena. It is also associated with anthropolinguistics and also covers the problems of evolution of human thought. In turn, mental also covers problems related to thinking and, therefore, also addresses ethnolinguistics in its studies. Since the thought process is also directly related to social processes, it also shares with sociolinguistics. Because "the brain of a person is a highly progressive matter of the thinking body, and the interaction of the human organism with the world therefore arises as a result of its service; thought is the action of the brain, the result of this thing. Thinking, thinking takes its content from the outside world".

The attitude of language and thinking, their philosophical interpretations, has long ago attracted the attention of scientists. In Particular, V.von Humboldt approaches language philosophically, arguing that language is influenced by thinking and, at the same time, thinking by language. Based on these views, he puts forward the idea that "language has phonemes, i.e. sound imagery, rather than sounds". It approaches language as a function of the organism. By the end of the 20th century, the theory of the cognitive approach to language appears in these views.

Since cognitology is a discipline that arises at the intersection of different fields of science, its field of research will consist of "research on the methods of collecting and applying knowledge". Cognitology (cognitive science) is the science of thought, the focal point of which is linguistics. Linguistic analysis is a type of cognitive analysis, its manifestation in a certain way. Because "Thought is the gift of being – the object, the phenomenon, and others, along with the activity of the subject, this gift of being is expressed through language, the sentence. Hence, thinking reflects objective being, reality, objective realism, the statement expresses that through the material of the language"

In fact, the science of cognitive linguistics originated in the second half of the 20th century as an observant, question-seeking science on the tools of the "artificial intelligence" system, which arose as a result of the development of Information Technology. This science is also part of the disciplines involved in human cognitive activity. A discipline that studies language as a cultural phenomenon, examining the construction of human knowledge and experience, is cognitive linguistics. Therefore, in linguistic sources, the word "cognitivism" is found in the definitions given to a special direction in science: "the task of cognitive linguistics is to acquire and preserve knowledge using language, practice and transmit language, in general, to conduct a deep scientific study of the language system and composition as a perception in the human brain".

Professor A.Mamatov walks the thought about the cognitive analysis of the language system, saying that "while cognitive science deals with cognition (cognition), cognitive linguistics studies the linguistic reflection, verbalization of cognition. A cognitive approach to language is a reflection of the structure of the language form, ultimately human consciousness, thought, cognition. Cognitivism expresses, according to its structure, the systematization of all types of knowledge that rely on human cognitive activity".

Professor G'.M.Hoshimov argues that " cognitive linguistics is an important direction associated with complex conceptual processes in the human brain, such as being by man, the perception of world reality through language, its study, that is, its perception, perception and perception through concepts"

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